

DEVELOPMENT OF FERROCEMENT ROOFING SHEET

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ABSTRACT

The cost of construction is increasing day-by-day due to increased cost of construction material such as steel, cement, sand as well as labour cost. Various types of roofing covers are available in market such as Galvanized Iron sheets used for roofing are costly, and difficult to handle. Steel is subjected to rust and theft. So to avoid these problems ferrocement roofing cover is one of the alternative. This project compares cost and weight of ferrocement roofing cover.

G. I. Sheet causes leakage problem after some use of it in rainy season, also it causes some problem for transportation like accident. We will develop alternative system for that. We will construct ferrocement roofing cover by varying number of layer. In this project we will achieve durability and economy.

KEYWORDS- Ferrocement roofing sheet, GI sheets, roofing cover, comparison of cost and durability.